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THE DIALECTIC OF TRUST AND INSTITUTIONS AS EMIGRATION PUSH FACTORS: ALBANIAN YOUTH AS POTENTIAL HIGH SKILLS WORKERS EMIGRANTS

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ABSTRACT

Albanian society is restricting and reforming the trajectory of emigration, as a movement, a phenomenon, and a relatively new flow, unseen since 1945 until the present day. Albanian emigration has been unique in itself, despite the hermetic regime (1945-1990) that emigration was totally forbidden, but even after the 1990s, it has been classified as a sending country of labour emigrants. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the trajectory of emigration has shifted, with a greater emphasis on highly skilled workers emigrating. Due to the current emigration situation in Albania, this research was driven to get the results of the main pushing factors of current Albanian emigration. The research aims to analyse the level of trust of university youth as potential to emigrate as high-skilled workers, in the institutions (such as government, judiciary, education, media etc.). Hypothesis is based on the lack of trust of university youth in the institutions, that convert them into the protentional high skills emigrants. To guarantee a national-level measurement of the university youth emigration potential, due to the mentioned indicators, the empirical data gained from the quantitative online survey research on the measurement of opinions of (N=1010) Albanian university youth, at the national level of (N=7) (all) public universities in Albania, in (N=13) departments on social sciences profile, analysed by the Statistical program IMB SPSS 26, in different statistical approach analysis, such as descriptive, frequency, and cross-tabs.

Keywords: *Emigration; Trust; Institutions; Youth as Protentional Emigration; Albania*

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Introduction

Albania, since 1990's till nowadays, has been a 'country on movement', by sending emigrants to different countries of the world, especially in Europe. 'Indeed, over the past decades, emigration from the Western Balkans has taken on impressive proportions: according to new OECD figures, almost 20 per cent of Albania's population today, for instance, has left the country within the first 15 years of this century. Young people are leaving their home countries in search of economic opportunities abroad (Esch, Palm, Brey & Hagemann, 2020). Instead, the primary pushing factors of Albanian emigrants, till Pandemic Covid-19, have been allocated in economic opportunities, but the trend of pushing factors has changed. The new trajectory of Albanian emigration has in focus 'a better life' for high-skilled workers, which means, more than 'economic' opportunities. Regarding this article, the research has been focusing on the insecurity that comes from lack of trust in institutions such as government, judiciary, education, media, election affairs, people, friends, etc., and has become as main pushing factors of emigration, as highly skilled young workers. 'Trust can also help foster adherence to challenging reforms, and robust levels of trust, along with healthy levels of public scrutiny, can help legitimise and protect democratic

institutions and norms. At the same time, high levels of trust in public institutions are not a necessary outcome of democratic governance. Indeed, only in democratic systems – unlike in autocratic ones – citizens are not only free to report that they do not trust their government but also encouraged to show 'sceptical trust' (Prats, Smid & Ferrín, 2024). 'To examine the essence of trust, the trust relationship needs to be embedded and contextualized in a wider context (Möllering, 2006). This research is focusing on analyse of trust or distrust is embedded in the relationship between young migrants and institutions through institutional encounters (Sundbäck, 2023), and the action of movement from origin country to destination countries as high skills workers.

Learning more about the characteristics of respondents expressing a lack of trust may be important to understand potential reasons for this lack of trust and implications in terms of political behaviour. Recent studies suggest people with a lack of trust are not generally politically disengaged and apathetic, and their lack of trust can stem from various reasons and manifest in different ways (Van de Walle & Migchelbrink, 2020). In Albanian society, a manifestation of lack of trust is leaving the country, and forming a continuous emigration of youth as highly skilled workers, during

the last five years. ‘Mistrust involves being sceptical and critically evaluating what public institutions do and how they govern (Devine et al., 2020). Distrust stems from deeply rooted beliefs and biases that lead to an automatic negative response towards public institutions, regardless of the behaviour or performance of these institutions, but with endemic cynicism and expectations of betrayal (Thomson & Brandenburg, 2018). While mistrust relates to scrutiny and accountability that critical citizens are expected to exercise in a democracy, distrust involves structural and emotional beliefs that are challenging to change with government policies and actions (OECD, 2021). In this research, the aim is to analyse the level of trust in the institutions and state bodies, to understand the factors of emigration, beyond the classical push factors that are universally accepted (see Reveistein migration laws). According to Giddens, ‘the encounters with ‘the face’ of the system are vital for trust shaping as they are ‘places of vulnerability for abstract systems, but also junctions at which trust can be maintained or built up’ (Giddens, 1990). That means, trust level is building during life experiences, and the expectations of youth of employment as high-skilled workers, meet their needs. In this research, due to the main hypothesis and research questions, the research aim is finalised by literature review, methodology, research field data findings and conclusion, as a continuation of it.

Literature Review on Trust and Emigration of Albanian Youth as Potential High Skills Workers

‘The Western Balkans as a region would need about 60 years to converge to the EU’s average income level, according to

World Bank estimates based on the per capita income growth between 1995 and 2015. Since 2012, 6% of the working-age population has left the region. In 2019 alone, every day, 430 individuals from the Western Balkans – a region of 18 million inhabitants – received a long-term residence permit in the European Union (Esch, Palm, Brey & Hagemann, 2020). It is necessary to define that Albanian emigration has been unique in itself, despite the hermetic regime (1945-1990), when emigration was totally forbidden, but even after the 1990s, it has been classified as a sending country of labour emigrants. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the trajectory of emigration has shifted, with a greater emphasis on highly skilled workers emigrating. Due to the current emigration situation in Albania, this research was driven to get the results of the main pushing factors of current Albanian emigration. ‘For the first time in post-communist history, during 2020-2023, the direction and the trend of emigration flows changed from low-skill to high-skill workers (Likaj, Kalemi, Pograzha & Bas, 2024). ‘While groups from all socio-economic backgrounds and levels of education have migrated out of Albania, in the last decade, brain-drain outflows have been on the rise. Youngsters in their 20s, including the best-educated and most qualified, are emigrating to advanced countries (Gedeshi, 2021). The Albanian emigration history during the last three decades (it is very important to stress it as post-communist emigration), the trends and trajectories of the emigration have changed quite rapidly and in expected situation. After the Pandemic Covid-19, the Albanian emigration faced a new form of it, the movement of youth as highly skilled workers. ‘The phenomenon of migration, a comparison of personal desires

driven by the current social, political, and economic situation as the push factors, is influenced by the contemporary world conditions of offering better life, security, and stability to the future for youth as high-skill workers (Likaj, Kalemi, Pograzha & Bas, 2024). The lack of trust or distrust due to the political institutions and bodies manifest with leaving the origin country of youth, toward the developing countries, where the establishments of these are more trusting in policies and strategies of human rights and actions. 'Public trust is an important indicator to measure how people perceive the quality of, and how they relate to, government institutions. Trust reduces transaction costs in governance, in society, and in the economy, nurtures political participation, and eases compliance with public policies (Putnam, 1993). Measurement of the level of trust in political institutions (political parties), governmental institutions/state bodies (financial institutions, police, judiciary institutions, government as a political body, fairness of elections) and 'trust' as a personal indicator in people, friends, and media.' The relations among the indicators analyse the current Albanian university youth emigration plan (for the last twelve months), initial steps, financial plan and connections in the host countries, and are tested by the measurement of factors influencing the decision-making to emigrate (such as economic crises, insecurity and hopelessness, search to gain the sense of economic and political stability, better services, less corrupted state, opportunities for better jobs, opportunities to learn and growth, to trust in governmental functioning and judiciary system and happiness as a push factor of this decision (Likaj, Kalemi, Pograzha & Bas, 2024). Even though youth play a fundamental role in the structure and

dynamism of emigration flows, due to the performance of the risk of poverty, youth as a social category undertake the willingness and decision to leave Albania. 'The main issue to consider is that unemployment is related to a decrease in happiness and trust, influencing increasing feelings of insecurity (Likaj, Kalemi, Pograzha & Bas, 2024). All these factors influence insecurities, and untrust of all public institutions, and are important to measure as indicators of push factors for the emigration of Albanian youth, as the background of the social and political situation. Albanian society and governmental institutions need a deep focus on the analysis of the 'emigration push factors of youth as high skill workers' and very concrete actions for the strategies of preventing the 'youth gap'. The emergence of reform in the field of 'emigration' and 'population shrinking' will prevent the disequilibrium of society and the weakness of state institutions and bodies, in the future.

Data Findings and Analyses

The research aims to analyse the *level of trust* of university youth as potential to emigrate as high-skilled workers, in the institutions (such as government, judiciary, education, media ect). Hypothesis is based on the lack of trust of university youth in the institutions, which converts them into the protentional high skills emigrants, as explained by the research statements:

- the lower level of trust of youth in institutions increases the desire for emigration,
- the lower level of trust of youth in institutions increases the implementation of planning for emigration as an action.

To reach a considerable number of users university youth, at the university level,

it was necessary to use online social platforms. Survey questions were uploaded to the Google Form Platform. For this reason, it was necessary to send via online platforms (communications platforms such as WhatsApp and email addresses) more than 2300 surveys and received back just 1014 of them. Selection was random, but oriented just to the students enrolled in social and humanities sciences. Just 1010 have validity, and 4 of them are half fulfilled, which makes them unvalued. Due to the public university student population in Albania, connections with academic staff, and the usage of the snowball method, influence a considerable number of research studies at the national level. The research and surveys extended from January 2023 to December 2023, in seven (all) public universities in Albania.

The empirical primary data gained from the quantitative online survey research on the measurement of opinions of (N=1010) Albanian university youth, at the national level of (N=7) (all) public universities in Albania, in (N=13) departments on social sciences profile, analysed by the Statistical program IMB SPSS 26, in different statistical approach

analysis, such as descriptive, frequency, and cross-tabs.

Population and Target Group Properties

The research instruments provide the data utilised by the online research survey, at the national level in seven (all) Albanian public universities, enrolled in bachelor's (498 out of 1014 or 49.1%) or master's programs (512 out of 1010 or 50.5 %). In the University of Aleksander Moisiu, Durres (UAMD), 280 out of 1010 university youth or 27.6 % (4 surveys are missing in most of the survey responses; for this reason, it is important to consider the validity of just 1010 surveys in total). Surveyed students enrolled in the University of Elbasan 'Aleksander Xhuvani' are 229 out of 1010 or 22.6%, in the University of Tirana 152 out of 1010 or 15%, in the University of Vlora 133 out of 1010 or 13.1 %, in the University of Shkodra 104 out of 1010 or 10.3%, in the University of Korca 'Fan Noli' 62 out of 1010 or 6.1%, and in the University of Gjirokastra (which as lowest enrolled students in national level) 50 out of 1010 or 4.9%.

Tabela 1: *Public Universities and Youth*

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	University of Aleksander Moisiu Durres (UAMD)	280	27.6	27.7	27.7
	Tirana University	152	15.0	15.0	42.8
	University of Elbasan 'Aleksander Xhuvani'	229	22.6	22.7	65.4
	University of Shkodra	104	10.3	10.3	75.7
	University 'Fan S. Noli' of Korca	62	6.1	6.1	81.9
	University of Vlora	133	13.1	13.2	95.0
	University of Gjirokastra	50	4.9	5.0	100.0
	Total	1010	99.6	100.0	
Missing	System	4	.4		
Total		1014	100.0		

Tabela 2: *Departments and youth enrolment*

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Department of Sociology	67	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Department of Pedagogy	120	11.8	11.9	18.5
	Department of Psychology	56	5.5	5.5	24.1
	Department of Foreign Languages	268	26.4	26.5	50.6
	Department of Management	118	11.6	11.7	62.3
	Department of Marketing	39	3.8	3.9	66.1
	Computer Sciences	24	2.4	2.4	68.5
	Information Technology	10	1.0	1.0	69.5
	Department of Law	144	14.2	14.3	83.8
	Department of Political Sciences	43	4.2	4.3	88.0
	Department of Communication	11	1.1	1.1	89.1
	Department of History	8	.8	.8	89.9
	Department of Social Work	102	10.1	10.1	100.0
	Total	1010	99.6	100.0	
Missing	System	4	.4		
Total		1014	100.0		

This research reaches the obstacle of studying university youth, who will graduate in education and social sciences, who are in the non-attractive professions of emigrants' acceptance policies in the development-hosted countries (such as medicine: doctors, nurses, and other health care professions). 'The only program of Technology and information, at the University of Aleksander Moisiu Durres, is a two-year bachelor program (with a profile of optic fibre installations), which was chosen because this profile is not on the list of preferred professions for the host countries in the EU. The intention of

including this department in the research was due to the gender balance (because it is preferable for males much more than female students).

As shown in Table 3, 641 out of 1010 or 63.2% of university youth, are female, and 369 out of 1010 or 36.4 %, are male. The programs of study that are the sample target group of this research have more female students enrolled than males.

As shown in Table 4, age group categorisation is divided into three, such as 18-19 years old (486 out of 1010 university youth or 47.9 %). The second age categorisation is 20-24 years old (303

Tabela 3: *Gender*

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	641	63.2	63.5	63.5
	Male	369	36.4	36.5	100.0
	Total	1010	99.6	100.0	
Missing	System	4	.4		
Total		1014	100.0		

Tabela 4: *Age*

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-19 years old	486	47.9	48.1	48.1
	20-24 years old	303	29.9	30.0	78.1
	25-30 years old	221	21.8	21.9	100.0
	Total	1010	99.6	100.0	
Missing	System	4	.4		
Total		1014	100.0		

out of 1010 university youth or 29.9%), and the third group is 25-30 years old (221 out of 1010 university students or 21.8 %).

Trust in public institutions and bodies

Questions for measuring the level of trust (as an indicator 'believe), as shown in the following table 5:

- Political institutions, such as political parties.
- Trust in governmental institutions such as financial institutions, the police, the judiciary system, and the government.

- Fairness of elections
- Trust in general, to people, friends and media.

The descriptive statistic of the trust level, as shown in Table 5, was used to measure the dispersion of trust indicators (due to governmental and political bodies), spread out in university youth responses. The trust of university youth, in this study, was measured regarding indicators such as trust in police, the judiciary, government, financial institutions, media, governmental institutions, political parties, fairness of elections, and trust in people generally and in friends.

Tabela 5: *Measurement of trust level*

Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
I trust in the Police	1009	1.00	5.00	2.2557	.79808	-.064	.154
I trust in the Judiciary	1010	1.00	4.00	2.2614	.65810	.397	.154
I trust in Government	1010	1.00	4.00	2.2604	.60598	.662	.154
I trust Financial Institutions	1010	1.00	4.00	1.9743	.67177	.084	.154
I trust in Media	1010	1.00	5.00	2.8238	.82733	-.611	.154
I trust in Governmental Institutions	1010	1.00	5.00	2.2228	.74291	.898	.154
I trust Political Parties	1010	1.00	4.00	2.0515	.74587	.155	.154
I trust in the Fairness of Elections	1010	1.00	4.00	1.7653	.61319	.309	.154
I trust in People	1010	1.00	5.00	3.3723	.66635	-.188	.154
I trust in Friends	1010	2.00	4.00	3.6455	.56588	.827	.154
Valid N (listwise)	1009						

As shown in Table 5, the highest mean distribution is seen in the 'trust in friends' (3.6455) and trust in people (3.3723), with Kurtosis of 0.827 (positive Platykurtic) and -0.188 (negative Platykurtic).

The lower mean is shown in the level of trust in media (2.8238) with lower negative Kurtosis (-0.611), trust in the Judiciary system (2.2614) with lower positive Kurtosis.

Kurtosis (0.397), trust in government (2.2604) with lower positive Kurtosis (0.662), trust in governmental institutions (2.2228) with lower positive Kurtosis (0.898), and trust in political parties (2.0515) with lower positive Kurtosis (0.155).

The lowest mean is shown in the level of trust in financial institutions (1.9743) with the lowest positive Kurtosis 0.084, and in the level of trust in the fairness of elections (1.7653) with the lower positive Kurtosis (0.309).

The lowest mean of being satisfied with the availability of public transportation, with house prices to buy or rent, with the education system, show most lower values in the responses and differ to the Kurtosis values. The economic conditions are not the only primary pushing factors of youth from Albania to their home country.

The low level of trust, as seen in Table 5, where the level of trust in the institutional and governmental bodies is very low, influences the decrease in happiness and security of youth. It is not just an economic crisis, but the current political and cultural anomic situation in Albania nowadays, the economic conditions are not the only primary pushing factors of youth from Albania, as their home country.

The low level of trust, as seen in Table 5, where the level of trust in the institutional and governmental bodies is very low, influences the decreased security of youth. It is not just an economic crisis, but the current political and cultural anomic situation in Albania nowadays, that pushes the current emigration flows of youth.

Potential emigration of university youth (Decision making and preparedness to emigrate)

Table 6 contains the measurement of the potential emigration of Albanian university youth and their plan to emigrate, by 1-plan for the last 12 months. 2-Initial steps 3-Financial plan. 4-connection in the destination country, with a frequency statistical approach.

Tabela 6: Decision to emigrate

During the past 12 months, did you think about leaving/moving out, either temporarily or permanently?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes, temporarily	497	49.0	49.2	49.2
	Yes, permanently	406	40.0	40.2	89.4
	No	107	10.6	10.6	100.0
	Total	1010	99.6	100.0	
Missing	System	4	.4		
Total		1014	100.0		

The questions related to the potential emigration of Albanian university youth were analysed due to the Frequency approach and cross-tabs between the two questions. As shown in Table 7, the highest distribution of the respondents during the past 12 months, think about leaving/moving out from Albania, temporarily

497 out of 1010 university youth, or 49.2%, and permanently 406 out of 1010 university youth or 40.2%. Just a few university youths, 107 university youth out of 1010 or 10.6%, did not think about leaving/moving out of Albania. 89.4% of university youth, temporarily or permanently, during the past 12 months think to emigrate. Potentially, this is a very high rate and shows the desire of youth to leave Albania, which is influenced by the factors found in Table 5.

Conclusion

At the moment of breaking the social equilibrium (and formation of social tensions), the level of trust decreases, and insecurities appear, resulting from various social phenomena such as emigration flows. Social actors reduce and eliminate tensions by manifestation of action, such as making decisions to leave/emigrate and form a new, social/better life. Albanian university youth, low satisfaction (with life and living conditions), and low trust in the state bodies and political institutions, due to the current, social, political and economic conditions, formed an elation among the variables, on the conclusion that happiness is the main push factor and a challenge for potential emigration of university youth in the future (Likaj, Kalemi & Bas, 2024). According to Giddens, the intersection of institutional encounters and trust is the arena for the interaction between the individual and the

abstractive system, which can be referred to as an access point. Giddens names two ways of interaction through these access points: 'faceless' and 'facework' commitments. In a faceless encounter, the service user interacts with the abstract system without encountering a person. In a facework interaction, the service user interacts with a real person in copresence (Giddens 1990). The faceless encounter is occurring in Albania, till Pandemic Covid-19, where the manifestation of emigration occurs as a pushing factor because of a low level of trust or lack of trust in governmental institutions and political bodies. 'The trust spectrum, differentiating between individuals indicating political disengagement and a pervasive cynicism toward the political system and public institutions, referred to as distrust, and individuals reflective of more critical assessments and a disposition to work within the political system, known as mistrust (Prats, Smid & Ferrín, 2024).

As seen in Table 6, 89.4% of university youth, temporarily or permanently, during the past 12 months think to emigrate. Potentially, this is a very high rate and shows the desire of youth to leave Albania. The emergence of emigration prevention and fulfilling the long-term needs of youth is the duty of the government and the establishment. As seen in Table 5, the low level of trust, where the level of trust in the institutional and governmental bodies is very low, influences the decrease in well-being of youth and security for the present and future life. It is not just an economic crisis, but the current political and cultural anomie situation in Albania nowadays, the economic conditions are not the only primary pushing factors of youth from Albania, as their home country. The dialectic of emigration comes from analysing this

phenomenon, just from economical perspective. The research shows that emigration has multidimensions pushing factors. If the level of trust in the institutional and governmental bodies is very low, influences the decreased security of youth, and the ‘disbalance in equilibrium in social life’ will be appear with the social tensions not by revolts, by demonstrations and manifestations

of abounding the origin country through legal emigration as high skills workers, and leaving behind the huge ‘gap’ among the age-group, in high skill market of employment, in the low dynamic of social life etc. It is not just an economic crisis, but the current political and cultural anomie situation in Albania nowadays, that pushes the current emigration flows of youth.

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Guide for Authors

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